

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPLEMENTATION OF AN ASYMPTOMATIC BACTERIURIA MANAGEMENT
ALGORITHM IN A LONG-TERM CARE SETTING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Problem: Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) is often misdiagnosed as a urinary tract infection and unnecessarily treated with antibiotics in a long-term care setting.

Method: Change project with pre and post evaluation.

Setting: A 99-bed long-term care facility.

Participants: Physicians, nurse practitioners, physician assistants, and nurses.

Innovation: An ASB algorithm was implemented through the following strategies: (a) In-service class for nurses with quiz pre and post; (b) Quality assurance meeting for HCP; (c) Nursing shift huddles; (d) Algorithm posts; (e) pocket-sized algorithm.

Results: Quiz scores increased from 34.4% to 81.1% ($p < 0.0001$) after an in-service class. After the implementation, the percentage of urine cultures (UC) that were ordered routinely without documented reasons decreased from 49.23% to 6.67% ($p = 0.0001$); ASB overtreatment rate reduced from 86.9% to 42.86% ($p = 0.0001$). The prevalence of ASB was similar pre and post intervention 74.19% vs 63.64%, $p = 0.1686$

Conclusions: The use of an ASB algorithm and an educational intervention is important in the reduction of inappropriate antibiotic use, especially in LTCF. Nurses play a pivotal role in the process of assessment and treatment of ASB.

Recommendations: Further evaluation in other types of settings will curtail antibiotic overtreatment, which contributes to the development of resistant organisms.

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BACKGROUND

Significance

Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) is characterized as bacteria presented in a person's urine sample but without any signs or symptoms of a urinary tract infection (UTI). ASB is different from a symptomatic UTI and should be managed with different approaches (Nicolle, 2016a). However, ASB is often misdiagnosed as a UTI and unnecessarily treated with antibiotics since bacteria is commonly present in patients' urine samples. (Nicolle, 2016a). One prospective study disclosed that 75% of patients received antibiotic for ASB even though they did not meet minimum requirements for initiating antibiotic treatment (Agata, Loeb, & Mitchell, 2013). Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report disclosed that about 40% of prescribed antibiotics were improperly used to treat ASB (Fridkin et al., 2014). The burden caused by the overtreatment is significant to patients and health care providers, both clinically and financially.

Definitions

Urinary tract infection can present as ASB or symptomatic UTI (McCance & Huether, 2014). ASB is defined as the presence of $\geq 10^5$ colony-forming units per milliliter (CFU/mL) of a single bacterium in a urine specimen obtained via clean-catch from a patient who is without urinary tract specific symptoms such as dysuria, frequency, urgency, bladder tenderness, or costovertebral angle (CVA) tenderness (Nicolle, 2016a). For women, confirmation by two consecutive urine tests is required. ASB is also defined as the isolation of ≥ 100 CFU/mL of a single microbial species in a urine sample collected via catheter from asymptomatic men or women. A symptomatic UTI is considered when bacteria are isolated in one urine sample from an individual who

presents urinary tract specific symptoms (Nicolle, 2016a). Some patients, with or without UTI symptoms, may have pyuria, which is the condition of the urine sample presenting \geq 10 white blood cells per high power field, with or without bacteria (McCance & Huether, 2014).

Prevalence of ASB

It is estimated that the prevalence of ASB is 1-5% in pre-menopausal women, 2.8-8.6% in women aged 50-70, and 10.8-16% in elderly women above 70 years old living in the public community environment (Nicolle, 2016b). If combining the conditions of elderly men and elderly women who live in the same community, the occurrence of ASB is 5-10 % and 10-20 %, respectively (Nicolle, 2016b). For patients living in long-term care facilities (LTCF), the ASB prevalence is 24-51% for women, and 16-41% for men (Nicolle, 2016b).

Outcomes of ASB

The existence of ASB was not found to be related to mortality or decline in renal function (McNulty, 2014; Nicolle et al., 2019). Bacteriuria nonspecific symptoms in more than 30% of ambulatory elderly and functional deterioration, renal failure, mortality, morbidity, and the symptomatic UTI did not appear to be associated with non-treatment of ASB (McNulty, 2014; Mody & Juthani-Mehta, 2014; Origüen et al., 2016). A prospective cohort study showed a significant improvement, and no observable adverse effects, in 71% of public community-living, budget-tight, elderly women who delayed antibiotic treatment intentionally (Knottnerus, Geerlings, van Charante, & ter Riet, 2013).

Effect of ASB Overtreatment

There is significant evidence to highlight the risk of misuse of antibiotics in ABS treatment. Cai and colleagues (2015) discovered that ASB treatment was associated with significantly higher incidence of *Escherichia coli* isolates resistant to ciprofloxacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. Empiric antibiotic use for ASB was also found to increase rates of *Clostridium difficile* infection and death (Belton, Litofsky, & Humphries, 2018). Furthermore, research shows that from 2008-2011 unnecessary antibiotic utilization resulted in an estimated 13 million dollars of excess cost in more than 500 U.S. hospitals (Schultz, Lowe, Srinivasan, Neilson, & Pugliese, 2014). Therefore, it is necessary to develop strategies for eliminating the treatment of ASB.

Local Context

The prevalence of ASB is estimated at 35% at a local 99-bed LTCF in southern California. According to an audit report from the facility in 2018, 75% of patients with ASB received unnecessary antibiotic treatment for a range of three to seven days. In order to curtail the use of antibiotics for ASB in the target facility, a change in practice is necessary.

Statement of Purpose

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement, and evaluate an algorithm for health care providers (HCP) and nurses to guide care and eliminate overtreatment of ASB in a LTCF (see Appendix A). The algorithm was created based on the most current ASB diagnosis and treatment guideline issued by the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA). The algorithm was designed for HCP (physicians, nurse practitioners,

and physician assistants) and nurses in guiding clinical judgement and decision making on ASB management clearly and easily. The aim was to promote the IDSA guideline adherence and decrease ASB overtreatment.

Supporting Framework

The Integration and Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Sciences (iPARIHS) framework was used to guide the implementation of the ASB management algorithm (Figure 1). The original framework, PARIHS, was introduced in 1998 and became one of the most widely used frameworks outlining the multidimensional aspect of the translation of knowledge into practice (Harvey & Kitson, 2015; Laycock et al., 2018). The revised iPARIHS framework has increased the focus on the facilitation process rather than the facilitation role and has also improved recognition of the central role of the individual health professional in directing the process and outcomes of implementation (Harvey & Kitson, 2015; Harvey & Kitson, 2016). These features align with the way in which evidence was used to decrease ASB overtreatment. Therefore, it helped both guide and analyze the process of implementing the ASB algorithm in this project. The permission to use this framework was obtained (see Appendix B).

Figure 1. The iPARIHS framework. From “Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in Healthcare: A Facilitation Guide,” by G. Harvey and A. Kitson, 2015, New York, NY & Abingdon, OX: Routledge., p. 50. (Reprinted with permission).

As illustrated in Figure 1, the iPARIHS framework has four key constructs: innovation, recipients, context, and facilitation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Innovation is a central construct within the framework and refers to the practice or intervention that is to be implemented. In this project, the innovation was the ASB managing algorithm. Harvey and Kitson (2016) pointed out that people rarely took new knowledge in the original form, such as clinical guideline, and applied it directly into use. The conditions of innovation, which can influence how new knowledge is likely to be recognized and accepted, include the sources, clarity, compatibility, usability, accessibility, and observable advantage. Therefore, for an innovation to be applied in practice, it is necessary to adapt evidence. The ASB algorithm can assist HCP incorporate clinical guideline in an adapted way, as it is simple, practical, and applicable to the practice setting.

The recipient construct refers to the stakeholders or people who are involved with and influenced by the innovation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Patients, providers, and nurses are considered recipients as they are the algorithm users and beneficiaries. Recipients' responses to innovation are largely dependent upon characteristics of the recipients, such as motivation, attitude, level of skills and knowledge, values and beliefs, authority, and time (Harvey & Kitson 2015). These factors are crucial for the successful implementation of an innovation. An objective of this project was to convey the importance of adhering to guideline for ASB patients. In order to update recipients (HCP and nurses) of the guideline and help them understand underlying rationale, educational methods (one in-service class and two shift huddles) were performed. A guideline-based

algorithm was distributed to offer the recipients not only the convenience of accessing the guideline but also the necessary decision cues in managing ASB patients.

The context construct is described as the setting where the innovation will be implemented and the factors (e.g., culture, leadership, collaboration, history, resources, and policy) which could have significant impact on the setting (Harvey & Kitson 2015). Context consists of inner (including local level and organizational level) and outer layers. In this project, the local level context was each patient-care unit, the organizational level context was the LTCF, and the outer context referred to the health care system. To gain support for implementing the ASB algorithm from inner context, meetings with the medical director, LTCF leadership, nursing managers, and educator was processed. In addition, the medical record department was very helpful with data extraction.

The facilitation construct is a unique concept to this framework. It is viewed as the active element that can translate new knowledge into clinical practice by evaluating, adjusting, and integrating the innovation and the recipients within the context (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Facilitation is the key to dealing with challenges, leveraging strengths in recipients and contexts, and subsequently maximizing the potential for successful implementation (Kitson & Harvey, 2016). Relative to this project, the facilitators included one infection disease nurse practitioner (NP) (this author, the primary facilitator, and novice) and one infection disease specialist (expert). The role of the primary facilitator involves creating a guideline-based ASB algorithm (innovation), validating the content of the algorithm with the infection disease specialist (expert), and developing a plan of action (e.g., educational interventions, pocket algorithm, algorithm poster) on

how to encourage HCP and nurses (recipients) to implement this algorithm and integrate the practice into this project facility (context).

In summary, use of a framework can help to evaluate both the course and intended outcomes of implementation of an innovation. The iPARIHS framework provides guidance on the design of the facilitation strategy and helps to identify factors, which may influence implementation. Successful implementation of the ASB algorithm into practice is an outcome of effective interaction among innovation, recipients, context, and facilitation.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

To learn the significant findings and scholarly contributions about ASB, a review of literature was carried out using electronic databases CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. The search terms included asymptomatic bacteriuria, antibiotics, UTI or urinary tract infection or urinary tract infections, risk factors or contributing factors or predisposing factors or predictor or cause, barriers or obstacles or challenges, algorithm, interventions or strategies or best practices or treatment or therapy or program or management, and combinations of these terms. Unless the available resource is limited or a study is sentinel and significant to this project, the search included the following criteria: adult, English language, research articles, peer reviewed, and published between 2014 and 2019. Studies focused on LTCF settings were considered most relevant. Studies confined to a pediatric population were excluded. The main themes explored in this literature review were risk factors for ASB overtreatment, ASB overtreatment interventions, and the role of an algorithm.

Risk Factors for ASB Overtreatment

Diagnostic Complexity

Differentiation between ASB and UTI is challenged by diagnostic difficulties. First, there is no gold standard diagnostic test for UTI. A hospital based prospective cross-sectional study of 367 pregnant women's urine samples found that leukocyte esterase and nitrite had low sensitivity (71.4% vs 57.1%) and low positive predictive value (PPV) (62.5% vs 80%) for symptomatic UTI; these values were even lower for ASB (50.0% vs 35% and 29.8% vs 62.5% respectively) (Demilie, Beyene, Melaku, & Tsegaye, 2014). Pyuria alone is also not sufficient to differentiate symptomatic UTI from

ASB. When pyuria exists without bacteria, it can be caused by interstitial nephritis, genitourinary sexually transmitted infections, tuberculosis, inflammatory disease, medication side effects, or physiological reasons (Wise & Schlegel, 2015). If pyuria exists with bacteriuria, it only suggests laboratory diagnosis of UTI, which does not confirm clinical diagnosis of UTI (Mody & Juthani-Mehta, 2014; Nicolle et al., 2019). However, the absence of pyuria is a good predictor for the absence of a UTI since its negative predictive value (NPV) is 90-100% although its PPV is only 30-40% (Kanna, 2017; Oikonomou & Alhaddad, 2016).

Second, many patient-related factors make it challenging to determine if or when bacterial colonization progresses to invasive infection. Atypical symptoms, chronic urinary symptoms at baseline, communication barriers, or cognitive impairment can influence the accuracy of history collection (Cortes-Penfield, Trautner, & Jump, 2017; Nace, Drinka, & Crnich, 2014). Falls and altered mental status (AMS) are often considered to be caused by UTI (Schulz, Hoffman, Pothof, & Fox, 2016). However, a system review disclosed that no clear evidence of the association between AMS and UTI was identified among available studies (Balogun & Philbrick, 2014). A prospective study among 397 suspected UTI episodes showed that in 80% of fall episodes did not have bacteria plus pyuria, which suggested that falls were unlikely to be UTI related (Rowe, Towle, Van Ness, & Juthani-Mehta, 2013).

Provider-related Barriers

Recommendations of current clinical guideline are against routine screening or treating ASB in community-dwelling or institutionalized adult populations, except pregnant women or patients undergoing genitourinary procedures (Nicolle et al., 2019).

Guidelines from different organizations all emphasize the necessary of urinary tract specific symptoms for diagnosing a UTI and prescribing antibiotics (Jump et al., 2018; Stone et al., 2012). However, HCP's decision to prescribe an antibiotic for a presumed UTI is still mainly influenced by urinalysis results or non-specific signs/symptoms, such as fever or AMS (Kistler et al., 2017; Kistler et al., 2020). Studies disclosed that the provider-related barriers associated with ASB overtreatment included attitudes (e.g. acceptance of guideline and outcome expectancy), lack of knowledge, and cognitive biases regarding perception of the clinical implications of bacteriuria (e.g. pyuria, gram-negative organisms, geriatric patients), as well as discordance between knowledge and practice (Lee et al., 2015; Trautner et al., 2014). Fear of complications, overcautiousness, anxiousness, insecurity in ambiguous situations, personal reassurance, expectation of the physician's role, hope of positive impact on patient condition, and having witnessed poor outcomes due to restrictive usage of antibiotics were also reported psychological factors that motivated physicians to inappropriately treat ASB (Eyer, Lang, Aujeky, & Marschall, 2016). In addition, external factors from time constriction, demands of nursing staff, patient expectation, adaptation to institutional culture, or peer pressure have been reported interfering with practice and contributing to ASB overtreatment even though HCP were willing to abide by guidelines (Eyer et al., 2016).

Ineffective exchange of information among providers, nurses, and families can also affect appropriate management of ASB. A nurse or a family member is usually the first person to notice a change of condition in a patient with cognitive impairment. Providers have reported that nurses or family members frequently demanded orders for

urine tests or antibiotic therapy but lack of inadequate patient's information (Eyer et al., 2016; Kistler et al., 2013; Zabarsky, Sethi, & Donskey, 2008).

Laboratory-orientated Management

A recent qualitative study identified the most likely reason for overtreating ASB was reflex treatment of pathological findings from urine tests without evaluating clinical conditions (Eyer et al., 2016). Urine cultures (UC) especially play a major role in treatment decisions. Results from an observatory study showed that antibiotics were prescribed on previously untreated cases 89% of the time due to positive UC, even though no significant difference in signs and symptoms were presented between treated and untreated LTCF residents (Sloane et al., 2017). In addition, urine color, clarity, and smell are often the reason urine tests are ordered, which drive unnecessary treatment (Schulz et al., 2016; Sloane et al., 2017). Studies detecting the association between urine smells/clarity/color and UTI are limited. Available evidence showed that urine clarity had poor sensitivity (13.3%) and low PPV (40.0%) in diagnosing UTI in women, while the PPV of odor was 54% for bacteriuria, and 28% for pyuria plus bacteriuria in LTCF populations (Midthun, Paur, & Lindseth, 2004; Foley & French, 2011).

Interventions Reducing ASB Overtreatment

Multiple studies have reported that educational interventions are effective in reducing ASB overtreatment. A pre-post study in a community hospital showed a significant decrease of monthly UC collection and proportion of ASB overtreatment in the post-intervention phase (Chowdhury et al., 2012). The multi-faceted educational intervention used in this study included pocket cards with an algorithm of ASB screening

and management, a promotional letter, and an educational seminar that presented clinical vignettes.

In a nurse-led prospective study in a LTCF, the educational strategies included pocket-sized reference cards, larger cards at each computer station, and educational sessions. Interviews from pre-intervention revealed that nurses' requests and decisions on UC was one factor that could cause ASB overtreatment. Therefore, the educational strategies were directed at not only primary care providers but also nursing staff, which was not commonly found in other studies (Zabarsky et al., 2008). Results showed a significant reduction in inappropriate UC, the overall rate of ASB treatment, and total antimicrobial days in the first six months after the intervention. These reductions continued to decrease in seven to 30 months post-intervention (Zabarsky et al., 2008).

In a quasi-experimental study of catheterized inpatients in general medicine wards and long-term care units, case-based audit and feedback, along with a diagnostic algorithm for ASB versus catheter-associated UTI (CAUTI), was used as an intervention (Trautner et al., 2015). The results showed decreasing rates of UC orders and the rate of ASB overtreatment. The researchers also surveyed providers during the implementation study and observed a significant improvement in the mean knowledge score of how to manage ASB and in scores for cognitive-behavioral constructs including self-efficacy, behavior, social norms, and risk perceptions (Grigoryan et al., 2016).

Some studies used bundled interventions that included a number of different methods. Irfan and colleagues (2015) conducted a controlled quasi-experimental study among medical residents and staff physicians at two teaching hospitals. At the intervention site, they implemented educational sessions, a UTI treatment algorithm with

emphasis on non-treatment for ASB, feedback on ongoing overtreatment, and a message attached to all positive UC reports pointing out that antibiotic use is only suggested for symptomatic patients. The results showed that the odds of inappropriate treatment of ASB decreased significantly at the intervention site, but did not change at the control site (Irfan et al., 2015).

In a prospective interventional trial, educational interventions using a 60-minute lecture and pocket cards were implemented in two community hospitals and one academic medical center. At the academic center, this intervention was also followed by a pharmacy-based audit and feedback, including a daily electronic alert of all positive UC and daily urine tests review with hospitalists (Hartley et al., 2016). Post educational intervention, the overall rate of ABS treatment significantly decreased and the greatest reductions were in ASB patients who were non-catheterized or without classic UTI symptoms. The pharmacy-based intervention resulted in additional 8.5% reduction and showed more effectiveness in catheterized patients (Hartley et al., 2016).

Moreover, interventions can target the routine UC. In a controlled before-after study, researchers implemented modified reporting UC, which means that a positive UC from non-catheterized specimens were only released upon request from the ordering physician, instead of being routinely reported (Leis et al., 2014). Following the intervention, the rate of antimicrobial therapy for ASB among non-catheterized patients significantly reduced (Leis et al., 2014). This intervention was not only effective, but also low-cost due to no additional education needed. To explore an intervention to reduce ASB overtreatment and cut costs, one study used a two-step model of UC ordering process in the emergency department (ED). The first step involved a UC order and

collection by nurses; however, the UC was not routinely processed by the laboratory until the ED physician ordered the second step: process urine within 48 hours (Stagg et al., 2017). An interrupted time-series analysis of the results showed a reduction in the weekly proportion of ED visits associated with processed UC, the monthly proportion of ED visits associated with callbacks for processing UC, the proportion of antimicrobial prescribing for urinary causes, and the cost of ED visit (Stagg et al., 2017).

Role of an Algorithm

Professional societies encourage HCP to use clinical practice guidelines. However, the complex content, the inconvenient layout, or the low applicability limits their implementation (Fischer, Lange, Klose, Greiner, & Kraemer, 2016). An algorithm is focused and user-friendly, which can reduce the complexity, increase the applicability, and improve the accessibility of a guideline. An algorithm has been combined with other interventional methods to help HCP follow ASB management guideline.

The algorithm used by Trautner and colleagues (2013) in the interventional study published in 2015 was developed through a two-phase research project where, in phase one, 10 HCP were assessed for the diagnostic cues they used when they differentiated CAUTI and catheter associated bacteriuria on 40 cases. Results showed only 53% of bacteriuria diagnoses were guideline-concordant, which indicated low level of accuracy and inter-rater reliability of the HCP's mental models for distinguishing CAUTI and catheter associated bacteriuria (Trautner et al., 2013). To redirect their mental models, a guideline-based algorithm was developed in phase two. Guideline authors and non-expert clinicians verified its content and face validity respectively, and its final version was used on 71 cases. Results demonstrated high inter-rater reliability of the algorithm between

expert and non-expert users and between two non-experts, which suggested the algorithm was able to recalibrate HCP's mental models and increase diagnostic accuracy (Trautner et al., 2013). Although this algorithm targets catheter associated bacteriuria, it can be adopted for ASB because HCP use the same mental models and follow the same guidelines when they manage bacteriuria-related care.

Researchers also used pre- and post-intervention comparison with a contemporaneous control to evaluate the predictive validity of this algorithm during its implementation (Naik, Skelton, Amspoker, Glasgow, & Trautner, 2017). The researchers determined that sensitivity and specificity was used to predict appropriate diagnosis of CAUTI and appropriate diagnosis of ASB respectively, while positive likelihood ratio (LR+) and negative likelihood ratio (LR-) was used to predict appropriate management of CAUTI and appropriate management of ASB respectively. The results revealed specificity and LR+ significantly increased at the intervention site in the post-implementation period, which indicated the algorithm improved accuracy diagnosis of ASB and CAUTI management. Although CAUTI diagnosis and ASB management showed similar improvements at both sites, antibiotics prescribed for ASB markedly decreased from 40% to 11% after implementing the algorithm. The researchers concluded that a fast and frugal algorithm could improve accurate diagnosis of ASB, reduce ASB overtreatment, and enhance guideline adherence through readjusting intuitive judgments and revising existing norms (Naik et al., 2017).

Review of Literature Summary

Asymptomatic bacteriuria continues to be one of the common findings in various healthcare settings. Despite evidence-based guidelines for ASB, overtreatment of ASB

remains widespread. The literature has disclosed factors associated with ASB overtreatment, including diagnostic complexity, provider-related barriers, and laboratory-orientated management. The literature also highlights different strategies to reduce ASB overtreatment. Education is a frequently used approach, but it is likely to be more effective in leading to sustained improvement when used as a component of a bundle of interventions than using alone. (Hartley et al., 2016; Irfan et al., 2015; Zabarsky et al., 2008) An algorithm has been reported as an effective tool to make a connection between knowledge and practice when adequate training is provided and corresponding changes of protocol are made (Naik et al., 2017; Trautner et al., 2013). Strategies of modifying routine urine tests are innovative. However, since they do not follow the traditional decision-making process, widespread utilization of these strategies across various settings needs strong evidence of effectiveness and supportive policy. In short, evidence demonstrated the efficacy of ASB managing strategies in certain settings as discussed above. It is important to adapt a particular strategy that is suitable for context. Considering this author's professional role, scope of practice, and work setting, an algorithm and educational initiatives were used for this study.

METHODS

The purpose of this project was to improve ASB guideline adherence and reduce unnecessary antibiotic treatment. Although HCP generally accept the recommendations of ASB guideline, they are not always familiar with its content and lack the ability to overcome obstacles and implement the guideline in practice (Naik et al., 2017). To bridge the knowledge-practice gap and promote application of the guideline, an action algorithm was developed based on the most current published guideline (see Appendix A). This algorithm was implemented and evaluated in a LTCF.

Design and Setting

A before-and-after intervention design was used in this project to evaluate the impact of the algorithm on ASB management. This project was undertaken at a LTCF in Southern California. The LTCF houses patients who are discharged from the hospital but are not well enough to go home and still require additional nursing and rehabilitation care. This LTCF contains 99 beds on two different units with 52 beds in one unit and 47 beds in another unit. The range of daily census ranges from 91-95 patients. HCP, who are physicians, physician assistants (PAs), and NPs generally visit patients within 24-48 hours upon admission and once every 30 days thereafter. Usually, one registered nurse (RN) and three to six licensed vocational nurses (LVN) are assigned for each eight-hour shift in this facility. One staff development coordinator is responsible for education and infection control for the LTCF. Common medical conditions for patients at this facility include dementia, stroke, complicated diabetes, heart failure, Parkinson's disease, chronic wound, osteoarthritis, and renal failure. The common events reported to HCP are fever, AMS, shortness of breath, poor intake, and falls.

Participants

The target participants were all HCP who order UC and prescribe antibiotics, including 10 physicians, three NPs and two PAs. Eight RNs and 20 LPNs were also included as participants since they are responsible for obtaining and carrying out orders for UC and antibiotic administration. It is the RN's responsibility to call the HCP to report patient condition changes and abnormal laboratory results, take telephone orders, and to administer intravenous medication. The LVN provides direct patient care, takes verbal orders, collects specimen for cultures, and administers oral or enteral medication. Unlicensed health care workers were excluded. A project flyer was posted at each nursing station and the doctor's office to invite HCP and nurses to participate.

Ethical Considerations

The administrator at the LTCF and the infection disease physician gave permission to proceed with this project (see Appendix C & Appendix D). Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained from California State University Fullerton (see Appendix E). All participants signed informed consent forms. No identifiable data were used and ethical standards were maintained.

Algorithm

The algorithm developed for this project was based on the most current ASB diagnosis and treatment guideline issued by IDSA for HCP who prescribe antibiotics. The algorithm was reviewed and approved by the infection disease physician. Since management based on laboratory results is one of the main factors prompting ASB overtreatment, the first step in the algorithm is to determine whether a patient should be screened by a UC. In the algorithm, it is emphasized that a UC screen should only be

carried out if symptoms are urinary tract specific or without other known causes, unless the patient is pregnant or undergoing a genitourinary procedure associated with possible mucosal bleeding (Nicolle et al., 2019). The next step in the algorithm is for HCP to decide whether they should prescribe antibiotics for a patient whose UC is positive for bacteria. It is recommended that a diagnosis of symptomatic UTI be established through a combination of assessments of clinical symptoms and an objective analysis of laboratory data (Nicolle, 2016b). Antibiotic treatment should be used for bacteriuria patients with urinary tract specific symptoms or non-UTI specific symptoms without other identified causes.

Procedures

After approval from the IRB on October 03, 2019, the project flyer was posted at the LTCF and distributed to HCP and nurses on October 04, 2019. Then the ASB algorithm was implemented on all units through the following strategies: (a) one in-service educational class was provided to nurses. The content of the education included current ASB guideline, appropriate indications for sending UC to the lab for analysis, differentiation between UTI-specific and non-UTI specific symptoms, potential adverse effects of antibiotic overuse, and how to use the algorithm. Informed consent forms for project participation were distributed, completed, and collected during the class time; (b) the algorithm along with a guideline summary table (see Appendix F) was introduced to HCP at a quality assurance (QA) meeting; (c) two shift huddles were used to introduce the ASB algorithm to nurses who did not attend the in-service class and reinforce the application of the ASB algorithm to nurses who attended the in-service class; (d) the staff development coordinator sent out a memo to nurses and HCP who could not attend the

in-service class, the QA meeting, or shift huddles; (e) the algorithm was posted in the each nursing station, the physician office, and the medication room; (f) a pocket version of the algorithm was distributed to HCP and nurses; (g) a 10-question quiz on ASB was given to nurses before the in-service class to assess the knowledge level about ASB; (h) the same 10-question quiz was given to nurses after the in-service class to assess the change of knowledge level about ASB.

Data Collection

Before the intervention, charts were retrospectively reviewed for patients who had a UC from January 01 to September 30, 2019. Primary data collected in this phase of the project included UC results, reasons of the urine tests (signs, symptoms, or other reasons), and status of antibiotic usage. Based on the IDSA guideline, urinary tract specific signs and symptoms are dysuria, frequency, urgency, suprapubic tenderness, costovertebral angle tenderness, pelvic discomfort, or gross hematuria; non-UTI specific signs and symptoms are fever $\geq 100^{\circ}\text{F}$, AMS, rigors, falls, poor intake, or change in urine characteristic (such as color, clarity, or smell). Patient data also included demographic characteristics (age and sex), orientation status, bladder control status, status of urinary catheter, and significant medical or surgical conditions.

During the intervention period (October 2019), participants' information—such as professional role, years of experience on the current role, and quiz score—was collected in the in-service class. After the intervention, patient data that was collected before the intervention (including demographic characteristics, UC results, reasons of the urine tests, and antibiotic usage) was extracted through chart review from November 01, 2019 to January 31, 2020.

All data were de-identified and documented on a spreadsheet (see Appendix G and Appendix H). A data dictionary was created to enable analysis (see Appendix I) All data were stored in a password protected computer by the author. All paper records were stored in a locked draw at the author's home only accessible to the author.

Data Analysis

Data analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 23 software (SPSS Inc, Chicago, Illinois). Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, and means, were used to characterize the patients, UC orders, and antibiotic use. Categorical variables shown in percentages (such as antibiotic treatment rate, knowledge score, or ASB prevalence etc.) were assessed for statistically significant differences pre- versus post- intervention by using a Chi-Square test. The ASB overtreatment rate was calculated as the ratio of total ASB cases that received antibiotic to the total cases diagnosed with ASB. The prevalence of ASB was calculated as the ratio of total cases diagnosed with ASB to the total cases with positive UC.

RESULTS

Participants

There were 25 project participants; three were physicians and 22 were nurses. None of the NPs or PAs participated in the project due to schedule conflict. Two physicians attended the QA meeting, and one physician signed the consent form while rounding on his patients. Nine nurses attended the in-service class; 14 nurses attended shift huddles; and one nurse attended both in-service and shift huddle. Among the 22 nurses, there were five RNs and 17 LVNs with 2 to 11 years of experience (mean was 5). The average score of the 10-question quiz was 34.4% before the in-service education versus 81.1% after the in-service education ($p < .0001$).

Patients' Characteristics

Table 1 displays patient characteristics. Fifty (14%) of 351 patients were tested for a UC before the intervention whereas 14 (8%) of 166 were tested for a UC after the intervention ($p = .3757$). Patients were similar in age, major medical history, orientation status, bladder control, and urinary catheter placement the before and after the intervention period except fewer patients had gastrointestinal disorders (21%, $p = .00001$) in the post-intervention period. Compared to the pre-intervention period, there were significantly more female patients than males tested for a UC in the post-intervention period (86% vs 64%, $p = .0005$).

Table 1

Patients' Characteristics

		Before	After	P value
Total % of Patients Tested*		14.24%	8.43%	0.3757
Age**	Range	33-97	53-99	
	Mean	75.06	72.71	0.6330
Sex**	Male	36%	14%	0.0005
	Female	64%	86%	0.0005
Hx**	CV	74%	79%	0.5100
	DM	58%	71%	0.0800
	Fall	16%	14%	0.8403
	GI	44%	21%	0.0001
	GU	58%	57%	1.0000
	Mental	38%	29%	0.2306
	MS	64%	64%	1.0000
	NS	78%	71%	0.3300
	Respiratory	26%	21%	0.5050
OS**	x4	42%	36%	0.4686
	< x4	58%	64%	0.4686
BC**	Continent	40%	43%	0.7742
	Incontinent	60%	57%	0.7742
Cath**	No Cath	82%	71%	0.0947
	With Cath	18%	29%	0.0947

Note. CV = cardiovascular; DM = diabetes mellitus; GI = gastrointestinal; Hx = prior medical history; GU = genitourinary; MS = musculoskeletal; NS = nervous system; OS = orientation status; BC = bladder control; Cath = catheter status.

* marks % is the ratio of the tested patient in each category to the total patients. ** marks % is the ratio of the patient in each category to the total tested patients.

Urine Culture

Table 2 reports UC ordering information. There were 65 UCs ordered before the intervention, during which 22,707 total bed-days occurred. This resulted in a UC order rate of 2.9 per 1000 bed-days. Since some patients received more than one UC test or more than one-time antibiotic, UC information and antibiotic use were counted as cases in this project. Of the 65 UCs, 7 (10.77%) were ordered due to urinary specific symptoms; 20 (30.77%) were ordered due to non-urinary tract specific symptoms; and 32

(49.23%) were ordered as part of routine lab work without any symptoms reported. Of the 31 positive UCs, 23 (74.19%) cases were diagnosed with ASB.

After the intervention, the UC order rate was 1.7 per 1000 bed-days (15 UCs during 8759 total bed-days), similar to the pre-intervention period ($p = .1034$). Of the 15 UCs, seven (46.67%) were ordered due to urinary specific symptoms; five (33.33%) were ordered due to non-urinary tract specific symptoms; one (6.67%) was tested as routine lab work without any symptoms reported. Of the 11 positive UCs, seven (63.64%) cases were diagnosed with ASB, fewer than the pre-intervention period though not statistically significant ($p = .1686$). The proportions of ASB cases among the total UC orders increased from 35.38% pre-intervention to 46.67% post-intervention ($p = .1131$). This may be mathematically related to the significant decrease of routine UC orders.

Table 2

UC order rate, UC order reasons, and ASB prevalence

	Before	After	P value
UC order rate	2.9/1000 bed-days	1.7/1000 bed-days	0.1034
UTSS	10.77% (7/65)	46.67% (7/15)	0.0001
RUC* N-UTSS	30.77% (20/65)	33.33% (5/15)	0.8796
Routine	49.23% (32/65)	6.67% (1/15)	0.0001
ASB Prevalence**	74.19% (23/31)	63.43% (7/11)	0.1686

Note. UTSS = urinary tract specific symptoms; RUC = reason of urine culture; N-UTSS = non-urinary tract specific symptoms.

* marks % in this category is the ratio of the test in each sub-category to the total UC orders. ** marks % in this category is the ratio of cases diagnosed with ASB to the total positive UC.

Antibiotic Use

Antibiotic use information is displayed in Table 3. Before the intervention, antibiotics were used for 36 cases; 20 (55.56%) of them treated ASB patients and 9 (25.00%) treated UTI patients. Twenty out of 23 (86.96%) cases that were diagnosed

with ASB were treated by antibiotics. After the intervention, antibiotics usage for ASB patients (three out of nine) significantly decreased to 33.33% ($p = .0017$) whereas antibiotics usage for UTI patients (five out of nine) significantly increased to 55.56% ($p = .0001$). Three out of seven (42.86%) ASB cases received antibiotic therapy, a significant decrease from pre-intervention ($p = .0001$). Figure 2 illustrates the percentage of ASB, UC orders, and antibiotic use before and after the intervention.

Table 3

Antibiotic use and ASB overtreatment rate

		Before (n = 36)	After (n = 9)	P value
Abx use*	Treat ASB	55.56% (20/36)	33.33% (3/9)	0.0017
	Treat UTI	25.00% (9/36)	55.56% (5/9)	0.0001
	Other	19.44% (7/36)	11.11% (1/9)	0.1131
ASB OT rate**		86.96% (20/23)	42.86% (3/7)	0.0001

Note. Abx = antibiotics; OT = overtreatment.

* marks % in this category is the ratio of the antibiotics use in each sub-category to the total antibiotic use. ** marks % in this category is the ratio of ASB cases received antibiotic to the cases diagnosed with ASB.

Figure 2. Percentage of ASB, UC orders, and antibiotic use pre and post intervention

DISCUSSION

This project implemented an ASB management algorithm in a LTCF to promote guideline adherence. The results demonstrated a significant reduction in ASB overtreatment with antibiotics after implementation of the ASB management algorithm. Another finding was that the average quiz score significantly improved after the one-hour in-service class, which indicated that an educational intervention could improve knowledge of ASB management. Additional methods used to facilitate the implementation of the algorithm included shift huddles, a QA meeting, posts, a memo, and pocket cards.

Unnecessary UCs have been reported as an important factor causing ASB overtreatment because it is difficult for HCP to ignore a positive UC (Lee et al., 2015; Sloane et al., 2017). A call to action on reducing routine UCs has been made (Leis, & Soong, 2019). The findings of this project showed a significant decrease in the rate of routine UC orders with a significant increase in UCs ordered for patients with urinary specific signs and symptoms. The total UC order rate and total percentage of patients who were tested also decreased although not significantly. These reductions were not influenced by the prevalence of ASB because the prevalence of ASB did not change significantly pre- to post- intervention. Efficacious interventions to reduce unnecessary UCs have been reported elsewhere (Keller et al., 2018; Munigala, et al., 2019; Stagg et al, 2018).

This project revealed the influence of nursing staff on ASB management. High prevalence of ASB and overtreatment has been reported in LTCF (Nicolle, 2016b). To manage care of patients in LTCF, HCP rely heavily on nurses' reports. Only three HCP

participated in this project, 20% of all HCP who treat patients at this LTCF. The rest of the 22 participants were nurses, 78% of the total nursing staff. This absence of full participation may be related to the difference in working schedules and the short implementation period of this project. HCP visit patients on a monthly basis while nursing staff take care of patients daily. It is therefore important to provide education to nursing staff in LTCF, and in this project, education increased ASB management knowledge. This finding was similar to others reported in the literature (Cooper et al., 2019, Haley & Fritz, 2019).

The algorithm emphasized the importance of patient assessment before ordering UCs and prescribing antibiotics. This is in accordance with the guideline and other tools, such as the 4 Moments of Antibiotic Decision-Making approach used by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) Safety Program or the consensus-based decision tool developed through a Delphi procedure (Tamma et al., 2019; van Buul et. al., 2018). Positive UCs should not be used as the gold standard to rule-in UTI. Instead, it should be used to guide the right antibiotic choice when the treatment is clinically indicated.

Limitations

This project has some limitations. First, few consents were obtained from HCP and it was not clear if HCP who did not submit consents applied the posted algorithm. Second, the awareness of this project may have resulted in amplification of the intervention. Third, the rate of UC orders due to non-urinary tract specific symptoms, such as AMS or fever, did not decrease after the intervention. This could indicate the need for further education on non-urinary tract specific symptoms. Additionally,

compared to the nine months pre-intervention period, the three months post-intervention period was short. The rationale for collecting nine months data before the intervention was to better inform the author about the population and problem. Since participants may have had greater commitment early in the intervention period, the first three months post-intervention might have shown the most impact from the intervention. It will be important to track the effect of the intervention as time passes to assess the sustainability and the need for booster sessions.

Conclusions and Implications for Practice

This project demonstrated that an actionable algorithm could be disseminated via educational strategies and subsequently promote behavioral change in reducing inappropriate UC orders and antibiotic treatment of ASB in a LTCF. Although the sustainability has not been evaluated, the interventions used to promote the algorithm in this project were low cost, could be easily repeated, and disseminated in other settings. Future efforts should be directed to evaluate the intervention more widely, in other facilities with additional health care personnel. Antibiotic overtreatment needs to be a priority to reduce the proliferation of resistant organisms and the treatment of ASB remains a focus especially in LTCF.

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APPENDIX A

ASYMPTOMATIC BACTERIURIA MANAGEMENT ALGORITHM

Adapted from Naik et al. (2017) and Nicolle et al. (2019).

APPENDIX B

PERMISSION TO USE THE iPARISH MODEL

From: Y. C. [REDACTED]
Sent: Friday, 17 May 2019 12:27 PM
To: Gillian Harvey [REDACTED]
Subject: Permission to use the iPARIHS model

Dr. Harvey,

My name is Yumei Yu Cao, a DNP student at California State University of Fullerton. I am working on my scholarly project and will be submitting the study for publication. I would like to ask your permission to use the iPARIHS model and the corresponding figure in this project.

Thank you for your consideration.

Yours sincerely,

Yumei Yu Cao, MSN NP

From: Gillian Harvey [REDACTED]
Sent: Thursday, May 16, 2019 10:53 PM
To: Y. C.
Subject: RE: Permission to use the iPARIHS model

Hi Yumei – yes definitely okay to use this figure. Good luck with your studies!
 Gill

Gill Harvey | Professorial Research Fellow

Adelaide Nursing School | Adelaide Health & Medical Sciences Building, Level 6 | Corner North Terrace & George Street | The University of Adelaide | SA 5005 Australia |

Tel: +61 8 8313 0267

Email: [REDACTED]

<http://health.adelaide.edu.au/nursing/> <https://www.facebook.com/uonursing>

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 SOUTH AUSTRALIA
 AND #42 IN THE WORLD***

*2019 QS World University Rankings

APPENDIX C

APPROVAL LETTER FROM ADMINISTRATOR

TO: Yu Cao

RE: Project "Development, Implementation and Evaluation of an Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Management Algorithm in a Long-Term Care Setting"

Dear Yu Cao:

The purpose of this letter of agreement is to show our support of your quality improvement project, development, implementation and evaluation of an Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Management Algorithm in a Long-Term Care Setting as a part of your Doctor of Nursing Practice education. After careful review of the above the proposal, your project may begin to implement at Extended Care Hospital of Riverside. You will also have access to pertinent data; no identifiable patient data may be used during the completion of this project. In addition, you may not remove any physical form of data from the facility. When findings are disseminated as part of your project write-up or related presentations, you will not identify Extended Care Hospital of Riverside.

If there are any substantial changes to your protocol or procedures, a new project proposal must be submitted for approval. A final report is expected upon completion of the project. If any project activities continue one year after approval, a brief progress report should be submitted for ongoing approval.

Please contact 951-687-3842 with any questions.

Roger Groves, Administrator

8171 Magnolia Ave., Riverside, CA 92504
TEL (951) 687-3842 • FAX (951) 588-2079
extendedcarehospital.com

APPENDIX D

APPROVAL LETTER FROM INFECTION DISEASE PHYSICIAN

Tejaskumar Naik M.D.**Infection Disease Specialist**

2083 Compton Ave Suite 103

Corona, CA 92881

Phone: 951-372-0039

Fax: 951-372-0108

TO: Yu Cao

RE: Project "Development, Implementation and Evaluation of an Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Management Algorithm in a Long-term Care Setting"

Dear Yu Cao:

This letter acknowledges that I have received the request by you to conduct a quality improvement project entitled "Development, Implementation and Evaluation of an Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Management Algorithm in a Long-term Care Setting." I have reviewed the referred algorithm. Based on the degree of risk, I approve of the project to be conducted.

If you have any concerns or need additional information, please contact me at 951-372-0039.

Sincerely,

Tejaskumar Naik M.D.

8/13/19

APPENDIX E

APPROVAL NOTICE FROM INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD

Titan Apps	Yu Cao <ycao17@csu.fullerton.edu>
HSR-19-20-97 - Initial: Approval Letter - Initial - Exempt	
irb@fullerton.edu <irb@fullerton.edu> To: dejung@fullerton.edu, ycao17@csu.fullerton.edu Cc: irb@fullerton.edu	Thu, Oct 3, 2019 at 6:12 PM
CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON	
<i>Office of Research and Sponsored Projects</i> P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238	
APPROVAL NOTICE	
<i>From the Institutional Review Board California State University, Fullerton</i>	
October 3, 2019	
From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair CSUF Institutional Review Board	
To: PI: Yu Cao	
Application No. HSR-19-20-97 Study Title: Development, Implementation, and evaluation of an Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Management Algorithm in a Long-term Care Setting	
Re: Initial Exempt Review	
The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(ii). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording). Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.	

Category 4. Secondary research for which consent is not required: Secondary research uses of identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, if at least one of the following criteria is met:

- (i) The identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens are publicly available;
- (ii) Information, which may include information about biospecimens, is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects, the investigator does not contact the subjects, and the investigator will not re-identify subjects;
- (iii) The research involves only information collection and analysis involving the investigator's use of identifiable health information when that use is regulated under 45 CFR parts 160 and 164, subparts A and E, for the purposes of "health care operations" or "research" as those terms are defined at 45 CFR 164.501 or for "public health activities and purposes" as described under 45 CFR 164.512(b); or
- (iv) The research is conducted by, or on behalf of, a Federal department or agency using government-generated or government-collected information obtained for nonresearch activities, if the research generates identifiable private information that is or will be maintained on information technology that is subject to and in compliance with section 208(b) of the E-Government Act of 2002, 44 U.S.C. 3501 note, if all of the identifiable private information collected, used, or generated as part of the activity will be maintained in systems of records subject to the Privacy Act of 1974, 5 U.S.C. 552a, and, if applicable, the information used in the research was collected subject to the Paperwork Reduction Act of 1995, 44 U.S.C. 3501 et seq.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
 Deanna Jung

APPENDIX F

CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF ASYMPTOMATIC BACTERIURIA

▲ Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB)

- presence of ≥ 1 species of bacteria in the urine $\geq 10^5$ CFU/mL.
- irrespective of the presence of pyuria,
- in the absence of signs or symptoms attributable to UTI.

▲ Recommendations

Patients Population	Screen for and Treat ASB	Comment
Pediatric	Against	
Healthy nonpregnant	Against	
Pregnant	Recommend	Suggest 4–7 days of antibiotics
Functionally impaired women or men	Community-dwelling or LTCF: Against	
Functionally and/or cognitively impaired, bacteriuria w delirium or fall, no systemic infection signs	Assess other causes, careful observation	Bacteriuric patient with fever and other systemic signs: initiate broad-spectrum antibiotics
Diabetic patients	Against	
Patients s/p kidney transplant	>1 month prior: Against	<1 month: no recommendation (knowledge gap).
s/p Nonrenal solid organ transplant	Against	
Neutropenia (absolute neutrophil <100 cells/mm ³ , ≥ 7 days s/p chemo).	No recommendation (knowledge gap).	
Impaired voiding following spinal cord injury	Against	Atypical presentation of UTI should be considered
With an indwelling urethral or suprapubic catheter	Against	
Undergoing Elective Nonurologic Surgery	Against	
Undergo endoscopic urologic procedures associated with mucosal trauma	Recommend	Initiate antibiotics 30–60 minutes before the procedure for a short course (1 or 2 doses)
Undergoing implantation of urologic devices or living with urologic devices	Against	All patients should receive perioperative antibiotics prophylaxis prior to implantation.

APPENDIX G

DATA BEFORE THE INTERVENTION

Hx	OS	BC	Cath	NITR	LE	WBC	RBC	Bac	UC	RUC	Dx	Abx	Notes	
1, 5, 7, 10, 11	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	NL	1	A1C 7.5, 07/27: Citrobacter Koseri 10-25,000	
1, 2, 6, 7, 11, 12, 13	5	2	1	1	4	3	2	2	4	3	ASB	2	02/15: multiple organisms, Macrobid	
1, 3, 4, 7, 9, 10, 11	5	2	1	1	4	3	2	2	4	3	ASB	2	03/01: Proteus mirabilis > 100,000; Amikacin	
1, 4, 7, 10, 11, 12	5	1	1	1	4	3	1	1	1	2	NL	1	01/10: E. coli > 100,000; Rocephin	
2, 5, 7, 8, 10	3	2	1	2	4	3	1	2	4	3	ASB	2	04/17: proteus mirabilis > 100,000; Keflex Δ to Levaquin	
1, 2, 8, 11, 12	5	1	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	3	NL	1	08/05 E. coli > 100,000; Cipro	
1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12	5	2	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	5	NL	1	09/12: E. coli	
7, 8, 9, 11, 13	5	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	NL	1	Fri 04/12 order Mon 04/15 lab; NG	
1, 6, 7, 8, 9	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	ASB	2	Bactrim; 09/10: E. coli
1, 2, 5, 7, 12	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	4	2	ASB	2	02/06: E. coli 25-50,000	
1, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	5	NL	1	06/05: NG; Lt PNA per CXR	
1, 4, 7, 13	5	1	1	1	3	3	2	1	4	1	ASB	2	07/03: NG	
2, 6, 7, 9, 13	2	2	1	1	3	3	1	1	3	3	NL	1	03/08: GNB < 10,000	
1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	3	3	5	NL	1	07/06: E. coli, Keflex	
4, 5, 7, 8, 11, 13	4	2	1	1	2	3	1	3	1	2	NL	1	09/11: Enterococcus faecalis > 100,000; Macrobid	
5, 7, 11, 13	3	2	1	1	3	3	1	3	1	3	NL	1	08/29: mix flora	
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 10, 11	4	2	1	1	4	3	2	2	4	1	UTI	3	09/10: E. coli; pt on ASA. Cipro	
6, 7, 13	4	1	2	2	4	3	2	3	4	1	UTI	3	09/23: MRSA 10-25,000	
7, 9, 12, 13	5	1	1	2	2	3	1	3	4	2	UTI	3	04/22: Klebsiella ESBL 75-100,000; ordered at 04/20, bactrim DS	
1, 3, 7, 9, 11	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	2	ASB	2	05/16: Lactobacillus 25-50,000	
3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 13	5	2	2	2	4	3	2	4	4	2	UTI	3	09/19: NG	
1, 3, 6, 10, 11	5	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	4	3	ASB	2	06/04: NG	
2, 3, 7, 11, 12	5	1	1	2	3	3	2	3	4	3	ASB	2	01/04: E. Coli > 100,000; Cipro	
1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 11	5	2	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	4	ASB	2	01/07: E. Coli > 100,000; Invanze	
1, 7, 9, 11, 12, 13	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	5	NL	1	01/17: yeast 25-50,000; PICC 01/18, Invanze & Difflican	
1, 2, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12	5	1	1	1	4	3	2	3	3	3	NL	1	02/01: GPC < 10,000	
5, 11, 12, 13	2	2	1	1	3	3	2	3	4	1	ASB	2	03/01: E. coli > 100,000; Macrobid	
5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 13	3	2	2	1	3	3	1	3	4	2	ASB	2	02/25: E. coli > 100,000; Keflex	
1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 11, 13	3	1	1	1	4	3	2	2	2	3	NL	1	02/13: E. coli > 100,000; Macrobid	
1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 12, 13	3	2	2	1	3	3	2	3	4	2	UTI	3	abd pain, KUB: constipation, 08/27: E. coli > 100,000, Keflex Δ to Rocephin	
5, 6, 7, 9, 13	3	2	1	1	2	2	1	3	3	3	NL	1	Fri ordered Mon lab, 04/15: E. coli > 100,000, Macrobid	
1, 5, 7, 11, 13	2	2	1	1	3	3	2	3	4	2	ASB	2	05/17 DC Foley, 05/31: Klebsiella ESBL > 100,000, Levaquin	
7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	2	NL	1	01/04: GPC < 10,000, CT urogram w/wo contrast 01/10.	
5, 7, 9, 11, 12	3	2	1	1	1	2	1	3	4	3	ASB	2	02/25: NG	
1, 4, 5, 10, 11	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	NL	1	07/11: GNB < 10,000	
4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13	3	2	1	2	4	3	1	3	4	1	UTI	3	On Eliquis, 08/14 E. coli > 100,000, Levaquin	
1, 5, 7, 11, 13	3	2	1	1	4	2	1	2	4	3	NL	1	04/10: proteus mirabilis > 100,000, Keflex	
1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 13	4	2	2	1	4	3	1	3	5	3	ASF	4	02/04: ↑ Risperdal 0.5 BID to 1 BID, 02/06: E. coli > 100,000, Bactrim DS	
1, 2, 5, 7, 13	2	2	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	6	3	ASF	4	03/25: multiple organisms	
1, 2, 6, 7, 9, 12, 13	2	2	2	2	4	3	2	3	4	3	ASB	2	09/04: E. coli ESBL, Cipro	
1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 9	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	NL	1	08/06 GNB < 10,000	
6, 7, 11, 12, 13	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NL	1	TSH 0.16, Na 160, 07/30: E. coli > 100,000, Rocephin	
5, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	2	NL	1	08/07 GNB	
2, 5, 7, 11, 13	3	2	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	2	NL	1	01/19: NG	
1, 6, 7, 13	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	2	NL	1	F/C DC On 01/31, 02/06: enterococcus faecalis	
2, 6, 8	1	2	1	2	4	3	2	3	2	3	NL	1	perineal rash, Nystatin powder, K 5.5, BUN/Cr 9.3/3.2 (23/0.93), 05/23: NG, Difflican	
1, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12	5	1	1	1	3	3	1	2	4	3	ASB	2	BUN/Cr 6/0.7, K 3.0, Rx: Renal U/S, cystoscopy, 06/05: yeast < 10,000, Keflex	
1, 2, 4, 6, 7	5	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	4	2	UTI	3	07/09: E. coli > 100,000, Macrobid.	
6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12	5	1	1	2	4	3	2	2	4	3	ASB	2	05/23: Klebsiella ESBL 50,000	
4, 5, 7, 9, 11, 12	3	1	1	1	2	3	1	2	3	3	NL	1	09/14: Yeast > 100,000, Keflex, Microconazole cream	
1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 9	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	NL	1	05/08: Yeast > 100,000	
6, 7, 11, 12, 13	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	NL	1	Fri ordered Mon lab, 05/20: Providencia stuarti > 100,000, Keflex	
5, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	NL	1	02/06: GNB < 10,000	
2, 5, 7, 11, 13	3	2	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	2	NL	1	Rt flank pain, 01/09: NG, Cipro	
1, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12	5	1	1	1	4	3	2	3	4	3	ASB	2	01/24: GNB < 10,000	
1, 2, 4, 6, 7	5	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	4	2	UTI	3	01/06: NG	
6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12	5	1	1	2	4	3	2	2	4	3	ASB	2	07/25: mix flora	
4, 5, 7, 9, 11, 12	3	1	1	1	3	3	1	2	3	3	NL	1	CXR: bil densities, 07/17: MF, Levaquin, WBC 17.5	
													06/03: enterococcus faecium VRE > 100,000, Zyvox	
													05/16: E. coli > 100,000, Ivanz.	
													09/02: E. coli ESBL, Invanz	
													05/01: Klebsiella > 100,000, Levaquin	
													01/07: proteus mirabilis > 100,000, Rocephin	
													03/21: GNB < 10,000	
													06/20: GPC < 10,000	

APPENDIX H

DATA AFTER THE INTERVENTION

pt ID	Sex	Age	Hx	OS	BC	Cath	NITR	LE	WBC	RBC	Bac	UC	RUC	Dx	Abx	Notes	
1	2	80	1, 2, 6, 7, 13	4	2	1	1	2	3	2	2	4	2	UTI	3	3	01/07 Proteus UTI, ↑confusion & lethargic. CXR neg, RCT
2	2	67	2, 3, 7, 12, 13	4	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	4	1	UTI	3	3	Bladder stone 3.5 cm, 11/19 E coli ESBL, lower abd discomfort, Nitrofuratoin
3	2	69	1, 3, 7, 9	4	2	2						4	1	UTI	3	3	dysuria, 11/19 E coli, Macrobid
4	2	99	7, 10, 11, 12, 13	4	1	1	1	2	2	1	3	4	2	ASB	2	1	poor intake. 12/03 E coli, no use.
5	2	63	1, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11	5	1	1	1	2	3	1	3	4	1	UTI	3	3	dysuria, 11/18: klebsiella pneumoniae, Bactrim DS
6	1	86	3, 5, 6, 7, 11, 13	3	2	2	1	2	3	2	3	4	1	ASB	2	1	urine retention, 12/03: alpha-strep, no tx
							1	1	3	2	3	4	2	ASB	2	2	chest congestion, 12/30 Klebsiella, levaquin, CXR neg
7	2	79	1, 9, 11, 13	5	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	1	1	NL	1	5	↓intake, ↑freq & cofusion, dysuria; NG; Macrobid
8	2	60	1, 6, 7, 10, 11, 13	5	2	1	1	2	3	1	4	4	5	ASB	2	2	leutocytosis (12.5, 12.0, 11.9), 12/04 Lactobacillus, Keflex. 13.6 post abx
9	2	75	1, 6, 7, 8, 11	3	1	1	1	2	3	2	3	2	2	UTI	3	3	gen weak, ALOC, fever, to ER, MF, levaquin
10	2	64	1, 4, 7, 11, 12, 13	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	2	1	NL	1	1	MF, dysuria, no tx
11	2	59	1, 3, 6, 7	4	2	2	1	4	3	2	3	4	1	ASB	2	1	retention, 11/27 E. coli, urology consult
12	2	53	1, 6, 7, 8.	5	1	1	1	4	3	1	4	4	2	ASB	2	1	shripm allergy, 12/27 E Coli, no tx.
13	2	91	2, 5, 11, 13	3	2	1	1	3	3	2	2	4	5	ASB	2	2	11/02 UA WBC 68 →11/06: Rx UA CS, blood CS, CXR → E coli, Bactrim DS
14	1	73	1, 6, 11, 12, 13	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	NL	1	1	1/11: PSA, UA & CS. PSA 3.3 (0-4); NG

APPENDIX I

DATA DICTIONARY

- Sex: 1 = Male; 2 = Female
- Orientation status (OS): x 0 = 1; x 1 = 2; x 2 = 3; x 3 = 4; x 4 = 5
- Bladder control (BC): 1= continent; 2 = incontinent
- Urine catheter (Cath): 1= no; 2 = Foley; 3 = suprapubic; 4 = nephrostomy drain
- History (Hx):
 - 1 = Diabetes mellitus (DM)
 - Genitourinary disease (GU):
 - 2 = Urinary tract infection (UTI)
 - 3 = Urologic diseases (benign prostatic hyperplasia [BPH], prostatic cancer, bladder control problems, stones, etc.)
 - 4 = Renal disease (chronic kidney disease [CKD], End-stage renal disease [ESRD], on hemodialysis [HD] etc.).
 - Nervous system (NS):
 - 5 = Dementia or Alzheimer's disease (AD)
 - 6 = Other nervous system (NS) disorder (epilepsy, cerebrovascular accident [CVA] with any residual deficit, Parkinson's disease, spinal cord injury, cerebral palsy, etc.)
 - 7 = Cardiovascular (CV) disease (hypertension [HTN], coronary artery disease [CAD], atrial fibrillation [AFib], congestive heart failure [CHF] etc.)
 - 8 = Respiratory disease (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [COPD], pneumonia [PNA], respiratory failure, asthma, etc.)
 - 9 = Gastrointestinal (GI) disease: (gastroesophageal reflux disease [GERD], percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy [PEG] tube, colon disease, etc.)
 - 10 = Fall
 - 11 = Musculoskeletal (MS) diseases (arthritis, gout, fractures, amputation, etc.)
 - 12 = Mental disorders (anxiety, depression, bipolar, schizophrenia, substance abuse, etc.)
 - 13 = Other (anemia, pressure ulcer, cellulitis, hypothyroidism, blind, hearing loss, obesity, etc.)
- Urine analysis (UA):
 - Nitrite (NITR): 1 = negative; 2 = positive
 - Leukocyte Esterase (LE): 1 = negative; 2 = small; 3 = moderate; 4 = large
 - White Blood Cells (WBC):
 - 1 = normal (0-5 per high power field [HPF]); 2 = 6-9/HPF; 3 = Pyuria (\geq 10/HPF)
 - Red Blood Cells (RBC): 1 = normal (0-2/HPF); 2 = abnormal ($>$ 2/HPF).
 - Bacteria (Bac): 1 = none; 2 = few; 3 = small; 4 = moderate; 5 = large

- Urine culture (UC):
 - 1 = No growth (NG)
 - 2 = Mixed flora (MF)
 - 3 = Single organism (SO) $\geq 10^2$ to $< 10^5$ CFU/mL
 - 4 = Single organism (SO) $\geq 10^5$ CFU/ml
 - 5 = Yeast (Y) $\geq 10^2$ to $< 10^5$ CFU/mL
 - 6 = Yeast (Y) $\geq 10^5$ CFU/ml
- Reason for urine culture (RUC):
 - 1 = Urinary tract specific symptoms (UTSS)
 - 2 = Non-Urinary tract specific symptoms (N-UTSS)
 - 3 = Routine lab
 - 4 = Prior to urological procedures (PUP)
 - 5 = Other (follow up treatment, new admission, prior to non-urological procedures, or family request)
- Diagnosis (Dx):
 - 1 = Normal (NL)
 - 2 = Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB)
 - 3 = Urinary tract infection (UTI)
 - 4 = Asymptomatic funguria (ASF)
- Antibiotic use (Abx):
 - 1 = No use
 - 2 = Used on ASB patients
 - 3 = Used on UTI patients
 - 4 = Used on ASF patients
 - 5 = Other